

Design Number	425510-001	
Class	15-10	
1.Mr. Manish Research Scholar, Institute of Food Technology, Bundelkhand University Jhansi, Uttar Pradesh - 284128 2. Mrs. Mahima Pandey Assistant Professor, College of Pharmacy, Gwalior Road, Ambabai, Jhansi, Uttar Pradesh - 284419 3. Ms. Sarika Gupta Associate Professor, Agra Public College of Higher Education and Research Centre, Agra, Uttar Pradesh - 282007 4. Dr. Anubhav Dubey Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Maharana Pratap College of Pharmacy, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh - 209217 , et al.		
Date of Registration	01/08/2024	
Title	AUTONOMOUS TABLET PACKAGING DEVICE	
Priority NA		
Design Number	425519-001	
Class	08-06	
Godrej & Boyce Mfg. Co. Ltd. Pirojshanagar, Vikhroli (West) Mumbai 400079, India		
Date of Registration	01/08/2024	
Title	MORTISE HANDLE	
Priority NA		
Design Number	425522-001	
Class	13-03	
Godrej & Boyce Mfg. Co. Ltd. Pirojshanagar, Vikhroli (West) Mumbai 400079, India		
Date of Registration	01/08/2024	
Title	KEY CARD SWITCH	
Priority NA		